

THE KINETIC POTENTIAL AND GRAVITATIONAL VACUUM HYPOTHESIS
A NOVEL COSMOLOGICAL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The model, while prescindng of the Cosmological Principle and assuming a frame of reference for the expansion of the universe, explains dark matter and dark energy.

The departure point from the Lambda-CDM model, and from General Relativity, is an objection to the way the observations which support the model are interpreted. These observations, made within the observable universe, should not be extrapolated to the entire universe.

We posit that the whole universe is expanding from a reference point, but we can only observe the expansion within the observable universe, without a frame of reference.

The observable universe is a sphere within the total universe which looks homogeneous and isotropic, looks as it were only expanding from within with no center nor boundary, but is also moving, as the universe expands from its center.

The main departures from the Lambda-CDM model and from general relativity, are that the universe is expanding from a center, the universe has a boundary, mass has inertia with respect to space, and that stellar velocities are close to the speed of light.

The universe, as an isolated thermodynamic system, has an enthalpy which is the sum of its internal energy plus the product of its pressure times its volume.

This pressure times its volume, plus the kinetic energy of the expansion, plus the potential energy, with respect to the center, add up to dark energy.

Dark matter is the relativistic increase of mass, due to the speed of expansion, the Lorenz factor.

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"It ought to be remembered that there is nothing more difficult to take in hand,
or more uncertain in its success,
than to take the lead in the introduction of a new order of things.
This coolness arises partly from fear of the opponents,
who have the laws on their side,
and partly from the incredulity of men,
who do not readily believe in new things until they have had a long experience
of them."

Niccolò Machiavelli

The Prince

"In my treatment of the planetary problem I chose these limiting conditions in
the form of the following assumption: it is possible to select a system of
reference so that at spatial infinity all the gravitational potentials φ_{ν}
become constant. [3] But it is by no means evident a priori that we may lay down
the same limiting conditions when we wish to take larger portions of the
physical universe into consideration."

Albert Einstein

Cosmological Considerations in the General Theory of Relativity

THE KINETIC POTENTIAL AND GRAVITATIONAL VACUUM HYPOTHESIS

Despite its wide acceptance, the capability of the Lambda-CDM cosmological model to explain the real dynamics of our universe is rather limited.

General Relativity, described mathematically by Einstein's Field Equations, and supposedly proven by observations, is at the foundations of the model.

Two fundamental aspects of the model are that the Universe is expanding at a low speed, at an accelerating rate, without a frame of reference, and that the universe is homogeneous and isotropic, the Cosmological Principle.

But the model, apart from not explaining the very beginning of the universe, does not account for dark matter and for dark energy, concludes that the universe has expanded faster than the speed of light (made possible since space is supposedly expanding from within) and there are serious objections to the Cosmological Principle. Among them, the Hubble tension, the Axis of Evil, Planck Mission data, which has led ESA to conclude that the anisotropies in the CMB are statistically significant and cannot be ignored, and many additional issues.

Very eloquent is Karl Popper's objection, "(Because I dislike making of our lack of knowledge a principle of knowing something.)" He summarized his position "as the cosmological principles were, I fear, dogmas that should not have been proposed".

We posit a model, The Kinetic Potential and Gravitational Vacuum Model, which by doing away with the Cosmological Principle, mainly by assuming the universe has a center and a fixed frame of reference, it explains dark energy and dark matter among other precisions. The model is internally consistent, it is consistent with classical physics and the laws of thermodynamics, it is consistent with the observations we have within the observable universe, and brings "naturalness" to our view of how our universe works.

With respect to General Relativity the departure point is an objection to the way the observations which support the Lambda-CDM model are interpreted. The observations are made within the observable universe, which then are extrapolated to the entire universe. They should not be, which is an as valid alternative as in the case they are.

The Lambda-CDM cosmological model was born with A. Einstein's "Cosmological Considerations in the General Theory of Relativity" describing a static, homogeneous, and isotropic universe and explicitly stating that the speed of displacement of the galaxies was very small with respect to the speed of light. The work of Friedman, Lemaître, de Sitter and others, and Hubble's observations, after considerable discussion and amendments, proved the model right, given the premises Einstein defined.

But they are premises, they are not based on real scientific evidence as Popper well noted. After the discovery the universe is expanding at an increasing rate and the failure of the model to explain dark energy and dark matter, it is worth questioning the cosmological principle and the premises; Einstein himself left the issue open as indicated in the opening paragraph.

To wean ourselves from today's Lambda-CDM model, a thought experiment is helpful.

We consider for the experiment a universe with a much larger gravitational constant (G) which should cause its mass to collapse some time after the big bang into a massive body, a blackhole or a neutron star, holding the entire mass of the universe.

How would this universe be like?

In addition to the massive body at its center, we would have gravitation expanding at the speed of light in all directions, creating additional space-time with a radius $r(t)$. In between the massive body and the sphere with $r(t)$ there would be an absolute vacuum with some radiation, and gravitation. Evidently there is a point of reference, a center, and a boundary (Figure 1). And where would be gravitation expanding into? It would be just expanding, creating space-time as it expands away from the center, with no mass in it. It is worth noticing that the boundary is forever out of reach since it is expanding at the speed of light.

Figure 1

But is our universe much different from the thought experiment universe?

In our universe, with the actual value of G , gravitation also has been expanding at the speed of light since the big-bang, and the existing energy and matter have allowed for the formation of clusters of mass resulting in galaxies, stars, and planets, the formation of elements heavier than beryllium and the predominance of free hydrogen and helium, instead of the monolithic core of the thought experiment.

As in the thought experiment universe, we can infer that there is also a center, that there is a boundary at $r(t)$, off limits, and that there is an absolute frame of reference for the universe set in space and in time, at the singularity at $t=1t_P$ (1 planck time unit).

We can rightly infer that the whole universe is expanding from the singularity. But we can only observe the expansion within the observable universe, as a fly inside a moving car. We see it expanding without a unique frame of reference, just like the raisins in a cake according to Hubble's observations, with no center and no boundary, just through the observation of the receding galaxies and CMB measurements; we cannot observe the expansion from the center.

Given that light and gravitation travel faster than matter, there should be a volume in the universe between where gravity has expanded to and where mass has expanded to. In this volume there is no mass, only radiation and gravity, for all practical purposes vacuum, like in the thought experiment universe vacuum space (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Therefore, the observable universe looks isotropic and homogeneous, but the entire universe, should not be, as Einstein himself thought possible in his 1917 seminal paper.

We posit then that the universe is not isotropic nor homogeneous, we propose the universe is an expanding sphere with radius $r(t)$, that is expanding from a center and has an edge, a boundary. Our observable universe is a sphere within the total universe that looks homogeneous and isotropic, looks as if it was expanding from within with no center and no boundaries, but is also moving, as we move, with the expansion of the universe. The center of the universe may or may not be inside our observable universe.

As an isolated thermodynamic system, the universe has an enthalpy which is the sum of its internal energy plus the product of its pressure times its volume.

$$H_{univ} = U_u + (P_u \times V_u) = KE + Q + U_g + R_{adu} + (P_u \times V_{olu})$$

And if there is a pressure level, there must be a pressure differential, this pressure differential times the volume of the Universe with matter, plus the kinetic energy (KE) of the expansion at relativistic speeds, and the potential energy (U_g), both with respect to the center, add up to dark energy. Since the speed of expansion is close to the speed of light, we are moving at that speed from the center, therefore the observable universe is also moving at that speed from the center, in addition to expanding.

These premises then are the main difference with the Lambda-CDM model, the Cosmological Principle does not hold, mass has an inertia with respect to a point in space, and stellar velocities are close to the speed of light.

The hypothesis then is that dark energy is part of the enthalpy of the universe and corresponds to those variables not considered in the current model, kinetic and potential energies with respect to the center of the universe plus its pressure times its volume.

$$\text{Since} \quad H_u = U_u + (P_u \times V_{olu}) \quad \rightarrow \quad P_u = \frac{(H_u - U_u)}{V_{olu}}$$

At the the big bang, all the energy of the universe was concentrated in the singularity and from that moment, the gravitational field has been expanding at the speed of light in all directions, creating space-time and leaving matter behind since its maximum speed must be less than the speed of light.

Therefore, in that region of space-time where there is gravity and radiation, but there is no matter, there is a vacuum which creates the pressure differential with respect to the volume where matter has expanded to. It is interesting to notice that at the edge of the Universe, where gravitation is expanding at the speed of light, time is not ticking, and that this boundary cannot ever be reached.

This pressure differential times the surface of the sphere which contains matter, creates a vacuum force (F_v) which pulls (sucks) matter out causing the matter bearing part of the universe to expand at an accelerating rate, trying to catch up with gravity. This is part of dark energy, smoothly spread throughout space and making the universe to accelerate. Despite its value is very low, it is it what causes the increase in the expansion rate.

The other component of Dark Energy is the kinetic energy of the expanding mass from the Big Bang itself. This is a very large percentage of Dark Energy considering the mass of the universe is expanding at close to the speed of light and likely the reason why E=mc² as it will be briefly analyzed later.

At the same time the gravitational force (F_g) of the mass and energy of the universe pulls the energy bearing part of the universe back together to the center.

Until about 9,000 million years after the Big Bang, this gravitational force was larger than the vacuum force ($F_g > F_v$), and the universe expanded at a decreasing rate; after that time, due to the inverse square law, the vacuum force became larger ($F_v > F_g$) and the universe started to expand at the increasing rate which has been observed, and will keep doing it for ever, although restrained by the relativistic effect (the Lorenz Factor) of the speed of expansion on mass and energy (Figure 3.)

Five billion years ago, R_{univ} was smaller so that $F_v = F_g$, and therefore the universe was expanding at a steady rate.

The center of the universe should not be within our observable universe, but it is still a question to be solved; in that case the centers should be close to each other, otherwise it would be evident through the Hubble parameter and CMB measurements, the observable universe would not look isotropic (Figure 4.)

We can visualize the model through a sturdy balloon filled with high pressure opaque gas placed in the center of a vacuum filled room. The balloon explodes (the Big Bang), and the gas molecules are hurtled in all directions propelled by the energy inside de balloon ($P \times V$) and sucked by the vacuum of the room (F_g is negligible). The visible universe would be a spherical volume limited by the visibility of the opaque expanding gas. This volume would be moving away from the center and its molecules moving apart from each other proportionally to their distance. It is interesting to note that about 70% of the mass of the universe is free hydrogen and helium.

Figure 3

Figure 4

SINCE THE RADIUS OF THE OBSERVABLE UNIVERSE IS 46.5 BILLION LIGHT YEARS, THE UNIVERSE MUST BE OLDER THAN 46.5 BILLION YEARS!

THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

VACUUM DARK ENERGY

The universe is an Isolated Thermodynamic system where

$$H_u = U_u + P_u \times V_u$$

$$U_u = Q_u + K_{eu} + U_g + Rad \quad (\text{Heat} + \text{Kinetic Nrgy} + \text{Potential Nrgy} + \text{Radiation})$$

$$P_{univ} = \frac{H_u - (Q_u + K_{eu} + U_g + Rad)}{V_u}$$

$$F_{vacuum} = P_{univ} \times A_{univ}$$

$$F_g = \frac{G \times M_{univ} / 2^2}{R_{univ}^2} \quad M_{univ} \text{ should consider dark matter}$$

$$Acc_{univ} = \frac{(F_{vacuum} - F_{gravity})}{M_{univ}}$$

$$Acc_{univ} = \frac{(H_u - (M_{univ} \times T_{univ} \times c) - \frac{1}{2} M_{univ} \times V^2) - (M_{univ} \times g \times R_{univ}) - (h \times f)}{\frac{4}{3}\pi \times R_{univ}^3} - \frac{G \times M_{univ}^2}{4 R_{univ}^2}$$

Muniv

(c = specific heat; V < c; Muniv includes dark matter; g = grav accel.; h = Planck's Constant; f = freq.; V and g measured wrt the center of the univ.)

Or we can determine the radius of the universe when the universe stopped expanding at a decreasing rate and started expanding at an accelerating rate, this is when Fv = Fg

$$\frac{(Hu - ((Muniv \times Tuniv \times c) - (1/2Muniv \times V^2) - (Muniv \times g \times Runiv) - (h \times f))) \times 4\pi \times Runiv^2}{4/3\pi \times Runiv^3} = \frac{G \times Muniv^2}{4 \times Runiv^2}$$

$$1/3 (Hu - (Muniv \times Tuniv \times c) - (1/2Muniv \times V^2) - (Muniv \times g \times Runiv) - (h \times f)) \times Runiv = G \times Muniv^2$$

$$Runiv = \frac{3G \times Muniv^2}{\pi (Hu - (Muniv \times Tuniv \times c) - (1/2Muniv \times V^2) - (Muniv \times g \times Runiv) - (h \times f))}$$

Needs to be noted that since Muniv >>>> (Fv - Fg), the effect of this variable is very small but is significant when the universe gets large enough and allows for the accelerating expansion.

Evidently these equations consider a classical rendering of the model and should eventually be modified by the relativistic effects on time, mass and distance (Lorentz Factors)

KINETIC POTENTIAL DARK ENERGY

Given the Lorentz factor equations, we posit that dark matter is the increase of the mass of galaxies due to the relativistic effect of the speed of the expanding matter from the center of the universe; and for the same reason, there should be time dilation and the universe should be much, much older than measured, which is consistent with the assessed size of the universe.

Since the universe is expanding from its center, a reference point, matter is expanding at a certain absolute speed with respect to its center. The hypothesis then is that dark matter is the result of the relativistic effect of speed according to special relativity, considering the equation

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

Since dark matter is about 6 times the visible matter mass, which we perceive as moving slowly or at rest, as Einstein considered, according to the equation, the visible universe should be moving at the speed of 0,97c with respect to the center of the universe.

And this is the most significant source of Dark Energy.

Figure 5 illustrates the evolution of the speed of expansion from the origin, from a speed 99.999999 % of the speed of light to 90% and the kinetic energy released, and its transformation into potential energy, materialized in the radius of the universe. It shows that if the speed of expansion has slowed down from 99.999999% of the speed of light, to 97% the speed of light, which

seems to be the present speed of expansion, the energy released is equal to the potential energy that the mass of the universe has today with respect to the center considering an average value for g of 0,1 m/sec².

Figure 5*

KEuniv AS SOURCE OF ENERGY FOR EXPANSION, MAIN COMPONENT OF DARK ENERGY.								
V/C	SQRT(1-v ² /c ²)	V	mass at rest	relative mass	1/2 x M x V ² joules	liberated energy M x g x h	h = E/M x g g = 0,1	
0,99999999	10000,00	299999997	3,625E+55	3,625E+59	1,63125E+76	0	0	Qu = Constant
0,99999999	3162,28	299999970	3,625E+55	1,14633E+59	5,15846E+75	1,1154E+76	9,73025E+17	Rad = Constant
0,999999	1000,00	299999700	3,625E+55	3,625E+58	1,63125E+75	1,46813E+76	4,05E+18	P x V = Constant
0,99999	316,23	299997000	3,625E+55	1,14633E+58	5,15836E+74	1,57967E+76	1,37803E+19	
0,9999	100,00	299970000	3,625E+55	3,625E+57	1,63092E+74	1,61494E+76	4,45501E+19	
0,999	31,62	299700000	3,625E+55	1,14633E+57	5,14815E+73	1,6261E+76	1,41853E+20	
0,99	10,00	297000000	3,625E+55	3,625E+56	1,59879E+73	1,62965E+76	4,49559E+20	
0,98	7,07	294000000	3,625E+55	2,56326E+56	1,10779E+73	1,63014E+76	6,35964E+20	
0,97	5,77	291000000	3,625E+55	2,09289E+56	8,86142E+72	1,63036E+76	7,78999E+20	today. R univ
0,96	5,00	288000000	3,625E+55	1,8125E+56	7,5168E+72	1,6305E+76	8,99585E+20	1,558E+21 mtrs
0,95	4,47	285000000	3,625E+55	1,62115E+56	6,58389E+72	1,63059E+76	1,00582E+21	
0,94	4,08	282000000	3,625E+55	1,4799E+56	5,88438E+72	1,63066E+76	1,10187E+21	
0,93	3,78	279000000	3,625E+55	1,37012E+56	5,33258E+72	1,63072E+76	1,1902E+21	
0,92	3,54	276000000	3,625E+55	1,28163E+56	4,88148E+72	1,63076E+76	1,27241E+21	
0,91	3,33	273000000	3,625E+55	1,20833E+56	4,50279E+72	1,6308E+76	1,34963E+21	
0,9	3,16	270000000	3,625E+55	1,14633E+56	4,17836E+72	1,63083E+76	1,42266E+21	

* The values included in the analysis are approximate and tentative and are included to better illustrate the way the model works.

In summary, dark energy is mostly kinetic energy stored in the relativistic effect of the mass of the universe expanding at close to the speed of light, driving the dynamic expansion of the universe.

In addition, the universe pressure times its volume accelerates the expansion.

Similarly, since the age of the universe is said to be 13,78 billion years, when considering a radius of the visible universe of some 46,5 billion light years, time dilation should be by a factor of 3,4. Plugging in these figures in the formula for time dilation, we obtain that the universe has expanded at an average speed of 0.94 c, which is consistent with the dark matter calculation and the lower expansion when FG was larger than FV.

$$\Delta t' = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

Also, the universe should be "contracted" in the direction of the expansion.

Therefore we have to consider that all the measurements we have of space, time, mass, and length are distorted by the relativistic speed of expansion of the universe.

An additional conclusion should be that there will not be a big rip, since the universe is not expanding from within, and that it will never expand faster than gravitation. Gravitation is expanding at the speed of light and matter is trying to catch up with that expansion, but it will never catch up.

And finally, it is worth noticing, as mentioned earlier, that the model seems to explain why $E=mc^2$. Since $E=mc^2$ and not $E=1/2mc^2$ or $E=3mc^2$, the Lorentz factor should be equal to 2, which means we are moving, the Earth is moving, at the speed of $0,86c$ with respect to the center of the universe.

CONCLUSION

The "Kinetic Potential and Gravitational Vacuum Model" is an ambitious hypothesis, but its consistency with the observations "within" the observable universe, its internal consistency, its consistency with classical physics and thermodynamics, and its capacity to give a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of the universe, including dark matter and dark energy, in a rather simple natural system, make the model worth considering.

The departure point is to change our view of the expansion of the universe based on the expansion of the observable universe, which looks homogeneous, isotropic and slow moving, but which should not be the case when considering the entire universe, which should be expanding from a point in space and time at the speed of light at its boundary, and its mass, expanding at close to the speed of light.

The model clearly is not a gravitational model, is rather a thermodynamical model and departs from general relativity, although it keeps some of its features such as described by John A Wheeler. Gravitation has a minor impact in the dynamics of the universe when compared to the kinetic energy of the expansion.

Finally, we should look for evidence to ratify the model by observation, mainly gravitation tidal effects, redshifts, time dilation and length contraction considering special relativity and an expansion from the center of the universe at relativistic speeds.

